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Abstract:

Production and trade performance of ginger in Karnataka - An economic analysis was carried out during 2020-21 in terms of profitability and resource use efficiency in ginger. Primary data were collected from 120 sample farmers of Shivamogga and Haveri districts. For analysis of data, applied cost concepts and Cobb-Douglas production function were employed. Total cost incurred were found to be Rs. 4,28,683.94/ha and Rs. 4,09,896.91/ha under Shivamogga and Haveri districts respectively, in case of Shivamogga district every cost i.e., Cost-A₁, Cost-A₂, Cost-B₁, Cost-B₂, Cost-C₁ and Cost-C₂ were more by 4.68, 3.37, 4.98, 3.60, 5.69 and 4.38 per cent, respectively than the Haveri district. The average per hectare yield of ginger under Shivamogga and Haveri districts was 545.03 and 513.14 respectively. The resource use efficiency has been determined by the Cobb-Douglas production function and R² (0.8783) value clearly indicates that fitted Cobb-Douglas production model is more useful and best fitted to the data.

Key words: Cobb-Douglas production function, Cost-A₁, Cost-A₂, Cost-B₁, Cost-B₂, Cost-C₁, Cost-C₂ and Cost-C₃

Introduction

Ginger is one of the first known Eastern spices, and it has been grown in India for millennia as both raw ginger and processed products like dried ginger, bleached dry ginger, ginger powder, sliced ginger, ginger oil, ginger oleoresin, ginger ale, ginger candy, ginger beer, brined ginger, ginger wine, ginger squash, and ginger flakes. Ginger is widely used in foods, drinks, preservatives, medications, and the fragrance industry and earning a sizable foreign exchange through export of ginger. In the Middle East and several European nations, ginger processed products have a significant export value. India is the world's leading producer of ginger (40,81,374 tonnes) and has the largest ginger-growing area (3,58,172 ha) during 2019-20. While ginger is cultivated in around 36 countries, and production is concentrated only in few countries of the world, among them India is a leading producer of ginger, having a share of 45.00 per cent in area and 35.20 per cent in production in the global map. This indicates that, India occupies a little less than half of the world's area of ginger and produces a little less than one-third of the world's ginger production. This clearly indicates the dominance as well as importance of Indian ginger in the global economy. While, Nigeria ranks second in terms of area and China ranks second in terms of production. Three countries namely India, Nigeria and China together occupy 77.30 per cent of world's ginger area. This shows that cultivation of ginger is concentrated only in few countries. This share went up to 83.37 per cent when Nepal is included. And remaining countries together occupies 5.89 per cent of world's ginger area.

India is recognized around the world for its better quality of spice and its exports. The other exporting nations in the world are China, Japan, Indonesia, Australia, Nigeria, Malaysia, Egypt, Spain and Tanzania. Spices accounts for 1.24 per cent of India's export earnings and 8.5 per cent of agriculture and its related products. Spices produced and exported from India are pepper, ginger, turmeric, chilli, tejpatt, cardamom, coriander, cumin etc. Ginger is primarily produced in India, China, Nigeria, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Thailand, Philippines, Jamaica and also cultivated in Australia, Fiji, Brazil, Sierra Leone and Japan. The biggest importers of Indian ginger are Japan and the USA. China accounts for the lion's share of global ginger exports. By and large, India exports whole and dried ginger. China, Nigeria, and Thailand are recently competing with India in the international ginger market.

Materials And Methods**Cost concepts**

The method adopted for computing the different cost concepts are described below:

Applied cost concepts:

For scientific costing, one has to have uniformity in the applied cost concepts used. They could be accepted and adopted across the country.

The definitions of various applied cost concepts have been given by

Commission on Agricultural Costs and Prices (CACP), Govt. of India, New Delhi. These definitions have found general acceptance.

They are summarized below:

Cost-A₁: All actual paid out costs for owner cultivator. This cost approximates the actual expenditure incurred in cash and kind and includes the following items.

- Hired human labour
- Owned and hired bullock labour
- Seeds
- Manures and fertilizers
- Machine / Implement charges
- Land revenue and other taxes,
- Plant protection chemicals and
- Other miscellaneous charges.

It does not include items like rent paid, estimated rental value of owned land, interest on fixed capital and family labour.

Cost-A₂: Cost-A₁ + rent paid for leased-in land

Cost-B₁: Cost-A₁ + interest on value of owned capital assets (excluding land, interest on long term govt. floated loans or securities)

Cost-B₂: Cost-B₁ + rental value of owned land + rent paid for leased-in land

Cost-C₁: Cost-B₁ + imputed value of family labour

Cost-C₂: Cost-B₂ + imputed value of family labour

Cost-C₃: (Cost-C₂ + 10% of Cost C₂)

Income measures in relation to different cost concepts

Farm business income = Gross returns – Cost-A₁.

Owned farm business income = Gross returns – Cost-A₂.

Family labour income = Gross returns – Cost-B₂.

Net income = Gross returns – Cost-C₂.

Farm investment income = Net income + imputed rental value of owned land + interest on fixed capital

Cobb-Douglas production function

Cobb-Douglas production function was used for estimation of resource use efficiency in cultivation of ginger, since it is widely used by various research investigators for studying resource use efficiency and they obtain precise results as follows.

$$Y = a x_1^{b_1} x_2^{b_2} x_3^{b_3} \dots \dots \dots x_k^{b_k}$$

It is converted into logarithmic form, so that it can be solved by the ordinary least square method. The logarithmic form of the Cobb-Douglas function is expressed as under:

$$\log y = \log a + b_1 \log x_1 + b_2 \log x_2 \dots \dots \dots + b_k \log x_k.$$

Where:

y = Dependent variable (Gross income)

a = Constant or intercept value

b₁ to b_k = are regression coefficients of X₁ to X_k variables and X₁ to X_k = variables used

Allocative efficiency

Given the technology, allocative efficiency exists when resources are

allocated within the farm according to market prices. To decide whether a particular input is used rationally or irrationally, its marginal value products were computed. If the marginal value product of an input just covers its acquisition cost it is said to be used efficiently.

The Marginal Value Products (MVP) was calculated at the geometric mean levels of variables by using the formula.

$$MVP \text{ } i^{\text{th}} \text{ resource} - b_i * (Y \div X)$$

Where,

Y- Geometric mean of the output

X- Geometric mean of i^{th} independent variable

b_i - The regression coefficient of the i^{th} independent variable

To determine the efficiency of allocation of the resources, the value of the marginal product obtained by multiplying the marginal product (b_i) by the price of the product and was compared with its marginal cost. A ratio of the value of marginal product to the factor price more than unity implied that the resources were advantageously employed. If the ratio was less than one, it suggested that resource was over utilized.

Results And Discussion

Cost structure in ginger cultivation

Cost and returns structure in ginger cultivation by Haveri district and Shivamogga district is given in Table 1 For the study of cost of cultivation of ginger, the applied farm management cost concept was used. In cost- A_1 , cost of seed (28.74 %), hired human labour (25.27 %), and manures and fertilizers (23.51 %) were the major costs in Haveri district, while these were 27.81, 26.22 and 23.65 per cent, respectively for Shivamogga district. In case of Shivamogga district every cost *i.e.*, Cost- A_1 , Cost- A_2 , Cost- B_1 , Cost- B_2 , Cost- C_1 and Cost- C_2 were more by 4.90, 3.49, 5.24, 3.74, 6.03 and 4.58 per cent, respectively than the Haveri district. The per hectare cost of cultivation (Cost- C_3) of the ginger crop (Table. 4.5) was higher in the case of Shivamogga district (Rs.10,58,849.33/ha) than that of Haveri district (Rs. 10,12,445.37/ha). Whereas the cost of production (cost per quintal) in Haveri district was -1.54 per cent (Rs. 30.29) higher than Shivamogga district. The reason for the higher cost of production in the case of the Haveri district than the Shivamogga district was the lower productivity of the ginger in Haveri district than Shivamogga district.

Table 2 indicates the returns obtained from the ginger cultivation. The productivity of the ginger was more in Shivamogga district (545.03 q/ha) than Haveri district (513.14 q/ha) with a yield difference of 6.21 per cent with respect to Shivamogga district. The gross returns included the value of main product of the crop. The gross returns were realized in Shivamogga district (Rs. 19,17,154.62/ha) was higher than the Haveri district (Rs. 17,73,343.51/ha). In Shivamogga district net returns per hectare was found to be 12.80 per cent higher (Rs. 8,58,305.29/ha) than Haveri district (Rs. 7,60,898.15/ha). The returns per rupee of expenditure were 1.81 and 1.75 in the cases of Shivamogga and Haveri districts, respectively (Table 4.6). Similar results were observed in Kadam *et al.* (2019) findings wherein, average per hectare gross returns of ginger observed were Rs. 16,63,975.00/ha.

In Shivamogga district, the gross returns, level of yield and returns per rupee of expenditure were higher than the Haveri district. This was attributed to the fact that inputs were used efficiently by Shivamogga district compared to Haveri district. Ginger production was more profitable in Shivamogga district than in Haveri district.

Input utilization pattern in ginger cultivation

Details of per hectare input use pattern in ginger cultivation is depicted in Table 3. It is confirmed that the total input cost required for per hectare ginger cultivation was Rs. 3,69,296.93/ha. Among all the different inputs used, rhizome cost contributes maximum share *i.e.*, 43.63 per cent (Rs. 1,61,128.70/ha) to total input cost followed by fungicide 21.00 per cent (Rs. 77,534.89/ha), chemical fertilizer 19.84 per cent (Rs. 73,285.83/ha), FYM 14.21 per cent (Rs.

52,479.27), pesticide 0.88 per cent (Rs. 3,262.39/ha) and weedicide 0.43 per cent (Rs. 1,605.86/ha).

Production function estimates of ginger

To examine the resource use efficiency in ginger cultivation, the production function analysis was carried out. The resource use efficiency has been determined by the Cobb- Douglas production function and R^2 value which have been presented in Table 4. The coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) showed that 87.83 per cent variations in gross income of ginger cultivation were due to the included variables, this indicates the Cobb-Douglas production model reveals the relationship between input used and of output produced and best fitted for the data. The results are on par with findings of Kadam *et al.* (2019) study wherein, R^2 for ginger was found to be 0.91.

The production function analysis explains that overall expenditure on variables like rhizomes (X_1), nutrients (X_2), machine labour (X_3), plant protection chemicals (X_4) and yield (X_6) influenced positively towards gross income generated by ginger cultivation and expenditure on human labour (X_5) influenced negatively towards gross income generated by ginger cultivation. This shows the utilization of resources pattern except human labour (X_5) is being utilized properly.

The details of production function analysis shows that variable resources like expenses on rhizome determined the coefficient regression value 0.842 followed by expenses on nutrients 0.092, plant protection chemicals 0.112, and yield 0.174 shown their positive and significant contribution on gross income of ginger cultivation. On the other hand, the expenditure on machine labour determined the regression value 0.051 shows positive and non-significant contribution on gross income and human labour determined the regression value -0.067 shown negative and significant contribution on gross income of ginger cultivation.

In nutshell, it is clear from the Table 4 that the expenditure on rhizomes (X_1), nutrients (X_2), machine labour (X_3) and plant protection chemicals (X_4) would contribute, significantly or non-significantly in explaining variation in gross income of ginger production.

It is also revealed from the data presented in Table 4 that the coefficients for nutrients (X_2) was positive and found statistically significant at one per cent level of probability. rhizome (X_1), PPC (X_4) and yield (X_6) were also found positive and statistically significant at five per cent level of probability. This showed that an increase in the use of these inputs would result in increased efficiency of ginger production. Human labour (X_5) was negatively significant at one per cent level, this may be because of their excess use of human labour than recommended level. Whereas, the coefficient for machine labour (X_3) though positive but found non-significant, indicating no significant effect of these variables on yield of ginger. Hence, it would not be profitable to further increase the expenses on these resources. The sum of elasticities ($\sum b_i$) was 1.18 which indicates an increasing return to scale.

Allocative efficiency of ginger production

The allocative efficiency of resources in the production of ginger has been depicted in Table 4. The ratio of marginal value of product (MVP) to marginal factor cost (MFC) in the case of rhizome, nutrients, machine labours, plant protection chemicals, and yield were 9.6239, 1.2142, 1.8274, 3.3940 and 6.0277 indicates that these inputs were under-utilized and still there is scope to use these inputs and increase the gross returns of ginger production. Where as in the case of human labour MVP to MFC ratio was -0.7891 indicates over-utilization expenditure on this input was more than the optimum level. Hence, withdrawal of some units of these resources might be profitable. The results are in conformity with the findings of Mathew *et al.* (2018).

Conclusion And Implications

Ginger is a one of the high investment spice crops, the seed (rhizome) cost accounted for around 30 per cent to the total cost in the study

area. Since the cost of seed material was very high, supply of rhizome at reasonable price may help the farmers to reduce the cost of cultivation similarly, labour cost accounted about 25 per cent to the total cost. Hence, mechanization may save time and labour cost.

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Table 1: Cost structure of ginger cultivation in Haveri and Shivamogga districts

					(Rs. /ha)
Sl. No.	Particulars	Haveri (n=60)	Shivamogga (n=60)	% Change	Average (n=120)
a	Hired human labour	1,40,868.22 (25.27)	1,53,300.55 (26.22)	8.83	1,47,084.39 (25.76)
b	Machine labour / implement charges	48,535.50 (8.71)	49,276.50 (8.43)	1.53	48,906.00 (8.56)
c	Seed (Rhizome)	1,60,172.91 (28.74)	1,62,626.78 (27.81)	1.53	1,61,399.84 (28.27)
d	Manures & fertilizers	1,31,028.16 (23.51)	1,38,283.44 (23.65)	5.54	1,34,655.80 (23.58)
e	Depreciation	16,773.79 (3.01)	17,858.03 (3.05)	6.46	17,315.91 (3.03)
f	Land revenue & other taxes	123.50 (0.02)	123.50 (0.02)	0.00	123.50 (0.02)
g	PPC	59,844.37 (10.74)	63,213.97 (10.81)	5.63	61,529.17 (10.78)
h	Interest on working capital @ 7%	37,831.43 (6.79)	39,669.09 (6.78)	4.86	38,750.26 (6.79)
I	Total Cost-A₁	5,57,346.46 (100.00)	5,84,682.76 (100.00)	4.90	5,71,014.61 (100.00)
II	Cost-A₂ (Cost-A ₁ + rent paid for leased in land)	7,70,500.77	7,97,377.21	3.49	7,83,938.99
III	Cost-B₁ (Cost-A ₁ + Interest on assets owned except land)	5,61,448.91	5,90,847.61	5.24	5,76,148.26
IV	Cost-B₂ (Cost-B ₁ + rental value of owned land + rent paid for leased in land)	7,74,603.24	8,03,542.05	3.74	7,89,072.65
V	Cost-C₁ (Cost-B ₁ + Imputed value of family labour)	7,07,250.54	7,49,895.85	6.03	7,28,573.20
VI	Cost-C₂ (Cost-B ₂ + Imputed value of family labour)	9,20,404.87	9,62,590.29	4.58	9,41,497.58
VII	Cost-C₃ (Cost-C ₂ + 10% of Cost C ₂)	10,12,445.37	10,58,849.33	4.58	10,35,647.35
Cost of production (Rs/q)		1,973.03	1,942.74	-1.54	1,957.89

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to respective total.

Table 2: Returns obtained from ginger cultivation in Haveri and Shivamogga districts

(Rs. /ha)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Haveri (n=60)	Shivamogga (n=60)	% Change	Average (n=120)
	Total Cost (Cost-C₃)	10,12,445.37	10,58,849.33	4.58	10,35,647.35
a	Main product(q/ha)	513.14	545.03	6.21	529.09
b	Selling price (Rs/q)	3,455.85	3,517.52	1.78	3,486.69
I	Gross returns (GR)	17,73,343.51	19,17,154.62	8.11	18,45,249.07
II	Farm business income (GR- Cost-A₁)	12,15,997.06	13,32,471.86	9.58	12,74,234.46
III	Family labour income (GR- Cost-B₂)	9,98,740.25	11,13,612.57	11.50	10,56,176.41
IV	Net returns (NR)	7,60,898.15	8,58,305.29	12.80	8,09,601.72
V	Returns per rupee (Considering Cost-C₃)	1.75	1.81	-	1.78

Table 3: Input use pattern in ginger cultivation in Haveri and Shivamogga districts

(Per ha)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Unit	Qty	Rate (Rs/unit)	Amount (Rs.)
1	Rhizome	1	Quintal	35.82	4,498.92	1,61,128.70 (43.63)
2	FYM	1	Tractor load	13.17	3,983.75	52,479.27 (14.21)
3	Chemical fertilizer	4	Quintal	7.84	2,336.25	73,285.83 (19.84)
4	Fungicide	8	Litre	2.77	3,503.42	77,534.89 (21.00)
5	Pesticide	2	Litre	3.06	532.58	3,262.39 (0.88)
6	Weedicide	1	Litre	3.29	488.83	1,605.86 (0.43)
7	Total					3,69,296.93 (100.00)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to respective total

Table 4: Production function estimates in ginger production

(n=120)

Sl. No.	Production variables	Co-efficient	MVP : MFC
1	Intercept (a)	1.35	-
2	Rhizome (X ₁)	0.842*	9.6239
3	Nutrients (X ₂)	0.092**	1.2142
5	Machine labour (X ₃)	0.051	1.8274
6	Plant protection chemicals (X ₄)	0.112*	-0.7891
7	Human labour (X ₅)	-0.067**	3.3940
8	Yield (X ₆)	0.174*	6.0277
9	R²	0.8783	
10	Returns to scale	1.18	
11	F- ratio	135.75	

Note: * Indicates significance at 5% level.

** Indicates significance at 1% level.